

Final Project Report

Balancing Producer and User Accuracy in Forest Boundary Classification Using Fuzzy Logic

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SIO 113 - Computational and Data Analysis in Geosciences

Professor May

May 2026

Abstract

This project uses Landsat imagery, NDVI, fuzzy logic, and an NLCD forest reference map to study a central question: where should a forest boundary go when the real landscape changes gradually? Each pixel was first given a fuzzy forest membership value from 0 to 1. Then I tested thresholds and chose a cutoff of 0.68, because it gave a reasonable balance between producer accuracy, which is about not missing real forest, and user accuracy, which is about not putting too much false forest on the map. The final fuzzy forest map had 19.7% strict disagreement with the NLCD forest reference. When close-call pixels near the threshold were counted as understandable boundary uncertainty, the agreement reached 87.2%. The main point of the project is that fuzzy logic gives a clear and adjustable way to explain a boundary choice in a map-making problem where the ground itself has mixed edges.

1 Introduction

A lot of effort goes into map making these days. There are many types of maps, like forest maps, wetland maps, flood maps, fire-risk maps, urban maps, and other kinds of maps. Many of these maps require clear boundary decisions for things that are gradual on the ground. Forests are a good example, because a forest usually fades from dense trees, to scattered trees, to shrubs, grass, roads, and open land. The map still has to draw a line somewhere.

The same problem shows up in other types of maps. Wetlands can fade into drier ground. Flood maps draw a line around risk even though risk changes gradually with elevation, distance from water, and storm size. Fire-risk maps turn a continuous hazard into categories. Urban maps draw a boundary around land that often fades from city, to suburb, to park, to open land. The problem is always similar: the real world gives a gradient, and the map has to produce a category.

Creating maps like these can be expensive and labor-intensive. National land-cover products use satellite imagery, image cleaning, cloud and shadow handling, seasonal information, classification rules, and quality checking. For example, NLCD production has used clean leaf-on and leaf-off Landsat composite images, because images from different seasons can help separate land-cover patterns [9]. That workflow is powerful and takes many steps.

A lot of modern image recognition also uses machine learning. Machine learning can recognize complicated patterns across many bands, seasons, and training examples. It also has disadvantages for this kind of boundary problem. A model can do well on past examples and then be weaker in a new place where the vegetation, shadows, terrain, or season look different. It can also act like a black box. The map maker may know that the model worked before, while the exact reason for one boundary pixel becoming forest can be hard to see. It can also be hard to tweak one useful parameter and predict exactly how the map will change.

This project handles that problem with fuzzy logic. The idea is to use a process that is more visible and less black-box. A normal final map puts each pixel into forest or non-forest. A fuzzy map first gives each pixel a membership value from 0 to 1. A pixel can be strongly forest-like, weakly forest-like, or somewhere in the middle. The cutoff comes later, after the middle ground is visible.

The main point of this project is that fuzzy logic gives a clear, adjustable way to balance a producer-side goal and a user-side goal. Producer accuracy is about catching real forest. User accuracy is about making sure that the pixels labeled forest are actually trustworthy for the map reader. User accuracy is the standard accuracy-assessment term, and it is also the consumer side of the map in a practical sense, because it asks what the user gets when they read the final product.

The simple version of the problem is shown on the next page. Imagine a patch of trees with a dense center and a sparse edge. A big square captures a higher percentage of all the trees, and it also includes more land that is not really tree-covered. A smaller square gives a cleaner forest area, and it leaves out more of the edge trees. This is the same tradeoff that shows up later in the producer and user accuracy graph.

Producer / User Accuracy Tradeoff

A forest edge has a dense center and a gradual, mixed outside edge.

Figure 1: Conceptual diagram of the producer/user tradeoff. The loose boundary captures more of the trees, and the strict boundary gives a cleaner forest label. Fuzzy logic keeps the middle values visible before the cutoff is selected.

The next step in the project is to make that same idea quantitative. I take a reference image, make a fuzzy membership map from Landsat NDVI, and then test thresholds. The goal is to find a threshold that trades off well between producer accuracy and user accuracy. After that, the same threshold can be tested on a different dataset, compared again against a reference map, adjusted, and tested again. Repeating that process across more reference maps would make it possible to find a stronger average threshold. In that way, the fuzzy workflow can help compress and streamline the intense workflow that goes into making these maps, while keeping the logic of the boundary choice clear.

2 Background and project question

The project question is: how can a forest classification balance the mistake of missing real forest with the mistake of labeling too much extra land as forest? In accuracy-assessment language, missing real forest is connected to producer accuracy, and extra false forest is connected to user accuracy [1]. These two goals pull against each other because a looser forest rule usually finds more forest, and a stricter forest rule usually gives a cleaner predicted forest class.

NLCD is used here as the reference map. NLCD provides Landsat-based land-cover information at 30-meter resolution for the United States [7]. In this project, forest means NLCD classes 41, 42, and 43: deciduous forest, evergreen forest, and mixed forest [8]. The fuzzy output is judged against that reference layer.

This project focuses on the boundary decision itself. A 30-meter pixel can contain a mix of trees, road, grass, water, bare ground, and shadow. A hard forest/non-forest label hides that mixture. Fuzzy logic is useful because it stores the mixture as a number before forcing a final label. That is the core logic from fuzzy classification: a class can be represented by degree of membership instead of only a hard yes/no answer [3].

3 Data

The main input image was Landsat surface reflectance. Surface reflectance is useful because it is corrected toward the light reflected from the land surface, rather than only the raw signal reaching the sensor. USGS describes Landsat Collection 2 surface reflectance products as 30-meter products [5]. That resolution matches the scale of the classification problem, where many pixels can contain mixed land cover.

The vegetation signal was NDVI, the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index. NDVI compares near-infrared light

and red light. Green vegetation usually reflects near-infrared light strongly and absorbs more red light, so NDVI is a common way to measure vegetation greenness [6]. The formula is:

$$\text{NDVI} = \frac{\text{NIR} - \text{Red}}{\text{NIR} + \text{Red}}.$$

For Landsat 8-9, USGS gives the NDVI formula as [6]:

$$\text{NDVI} = \frac{\text{Band 5} - \text{Band 4}}{\text{Band 5} + \text{Band 4}}.$$

The reference layer was the NLCD forest/non-forest map. The NLCD forest classes were grouped together so that the comparison would be binary: forest or non-forest. That makes the project about one clear boundary problem.

4 Method

The workflow had five main steps.

1. Clip the Landsat and NLCD layers to the same study area.
2. Align the rasters so the pixels match spatially.
3. Calculate NDVI from the Landsat red and near-infrared bands.
4. Convert NDVI into a fuzzy forest membership map.
5. Test membership thresholds against the NLCD reference map.

The fuzzy membership step can be explained as a ramp. Low NDVI values receive forest membership near 0. High NDVI values receive forest membership near 1. Middle NDVI values receive middle membership values. One simple version of that rule is:

$$\mu_F = \frac{\text{NDVI} - \text{low}}{\text{high} - \text{low}},$$

where μ_F is the fuzzy forest membership value. Values below 0 are clipped to 0, and values above 1 are clipped to 1. The output is a surface of forest-likeness.

After the membership map is made, a threshold turns it into a final map. With the selected threshold of 0.68, pixels with membership values at or above 0.68 are labeled forest, and pixels below 0.68 are labeled non-forest.

The accuracy check uses the same idea as an error matrix in remote sensing [1]. The two main formulas are:

$$\text{Producer accuracy} = \frac{\text{correct forest pixels}}{\text{all reference forest pixels}},$$

$$\text{User accuracy} = \frac{\text{correct forest pixels}}{\text{all predicted forest pixels}}.$$

Producer accuracy asks how much reference forest was found. User accuracy asks how reliable the predicted forest pixels were. A low threshold usually improves producer accuracy because it captures more forest. A high threshold usually improves user accuracy because it keeps the predicted forest class more selective. The selected cutoff is the point where that tradeoff was reasonable for this study area.

5 Results at a glance

Result	Value	Meaning
Selected fuzzy threshold	0.68	The cutoff used to turn fuzzy membership into forest/non-forest.
Strict disagreement	19.7%	Pixels where the final fuzzy map and NLCD reference gave different labels.
Strict agreement	80.3%	Pixels where the two maps gave the same label under the hard cutoff.
Close-call agreement	87.2%	Agreement when pixels close to the cutoff are treated as boundary uncertainty.

Landsat Natural-Color Context

Natural-color Landsat context map. Dark green areas are mostly forested terrain, and brighter areas are more open or developed. This is the landscape before the data are converted into NDVI values and forest membership values.

Landsat NDVI

NDVI map. This step moves the project from normal visual color into a vegetation-strength signal. Higher NDVI values generally mean stronger green vegetation, although NDVI can also respond to shrubs, grass, crops, wetland plants, and other green surfaces.

Fuzzy Forest Membership

Fuzzy forest membership map. Each pixel keeps a value from 0 to 1 before the final yes/no forest label is chosen, so the mixed boundary stays visible.

NLCD Forest/Non-Forest Reference

NLCD forest reference map. This map checks the fuzzy output. The forest category combines NLCD classes 41, 42, and 43, so the comparison is a hard forest/non-forest test.

Producer and User Accuracy Tradeoff

This graph is the math version of the square diagram from the introduction. As the threshold becomes stricter, producer accuracy decreases because more reference forest is missed. User accuracy increases because the pixels left in the forest class are more selective.

I chose 0.68 because it gave a reasonable balance between not missing real forest and not adding too much false forest.

Final Fuzzy Forest Map (threshold 0.68)

Final fuzzy forest map after the 0.68 threshold is applied. This is the final product from the fuzzy workflow, with membership values converted into hard forest/non-forest labels for direct comparison to NLCD.

Strict Disagreement: 19.7%

Strict disagreement map. Gray pixels show agreement between the final fuzzy map and the NLCD reference. Orange pixels are missed NLCD forest, and purple pixels are false fuzzy forest. Strict disagreement is 19.7%, so strict agreement is 80.3%.

Agreement If Close Calls Count: 87.2%

Close-call agreement map. A close call is a pixel that disagrees under the hard label while its fuzzy membership is still close to the 0.68 cutoff. These pixels mark the sensitive boundary zone. Same-answer pixels plus close-call pixels reach 87.2% agreement.

Threshold Uncertainty Zone (threshold 0.68)

Threshold uncertainty zone. Yellow pixels are within plus or minus 0.10 of the selected threshold, so they are the pixels most likely to flip if the cutoff is adjusted slightly.

Threshold summary panel. This view connects the numerical threshold choice with the spatial pattern of agreement, disagreement, and close-call boundary pixels.

Landsat Natural Color

NLCD Forest Reference

Selected Fuzzy Forest Map

Strict Disagreement: 19.7%

Final four-part comparison. This all-in-one view puts the original context, the NLCD reference, the selected fuzzy forest map, and the disagreement map together, so the whole project output can be seen at a glance.

Reference Map and Final Fuzzy Map

Final comparison: Side-by-side print comparison of the NLCD forest reference and the final fuzzy forest map. The NLCD forest reference is the map used to check the fuzzy output; the final fuzzy map is produced separately from Landsat NDVI using the selected threshold of 0.68.

6 Discussion

The results show why fuzzy logic is useful for forest boundary classification. A regular final map has to choose forest or non-forest for every pixel. The membership map shows that many pixels are somewhere in the middle. Those middle pixels often occur near roads, openings, sparse tree edges, hill shadows, and mixed land-cover areas.

The selected threshold of 0.68 is a practical cutoff for this study area. A lower threshold would capture more reference forest and raise producer accuracy. A higher threshold would make the predicted forest class more selective and raise user accuracy. The graph makes that tradeoff visible, so the cutoff can be explained. The threshold is not hidden inside a trained model or buried in a complicated set of rules.

The strict disagreement value of 19.7% shows that the final fuzzy map and the NLCD reference differ across about one-fifth of the study-area pixels. The close-call result adds an important interpretation. When pixels near the threshold are treated as uncertain boundary pixels, agreement rises to 87.2%. That result fits the logic of fuzzy classification, because many of the differences are near the kind of edge where a hard boundary is naturally hard to place.

The uncertainty-zone map is important for map use. In a regular forest/non-forest map, every forest pixel can look equally certain. In this project, the uncertainty map shows which pixels depend most on the cutoff. That gives the map reader more information than the final binary map alone.

This also explains why the project should be seen as a boundary-choice workflow. NLCD is the reference layer used to evaluate the fuzzy output. The fuzzy method gives a visible way to choose and explain a threshold. The useful part is the ability to see the membership map, test the threshold, look at the producer/user balance, and then repeat the same process on more reference maps.

7 Limitations

This method has limits. NDVI measures vegetation greenness, so it can respond to forests, shrubs, grass, crops, wetlands, and other green surfaces. It can also be affected by shadows, terrain, water, season, sensor noise, and atmospheric conditions. A forest classifier based only on NDVI is simple and transparent, and it cannot capture every detail that a larger land-cover workflow can capture.

The reference layer also matters. NLCD is a strong national land-cover product, and it is still an interpreted map made from data, rules, algorithms, and checking. A comparison against NLCD is a comparison against that reference product. A field-checked reference dataset would give an even stronger accuracy test.

The threshold was chosen for one study area. A stronger version of this project would test the same process in many different places and across more dates. The workflow could use one area for threshold selection, another area for testing, and then repeat across many public reference maps. That would show whether 0.68 is only a good cutoff for this example or whether it stays reliable on average.

8 Conclusion

This project asked how a forest classification should balance missing real forest and labeling extra land as forest. Fuzzy logic gives a direct way to handle that question. First, each pixel receives a forest membership value. Then a threshold turns the membership map into a final forest/non-forest product. The selected threshold of 0.68 gave a reasonable balance between producer accuracy and user accuracy in this study area.

The final output followed much of the same broad pattern as the NLCD forest reference. The strict disagreement was 19.7%, and the agreement rose to 87.2% when close-call boundary pixels were counted. The difference between those two numbers is important because it shows that many disagreements are tied to threshold-sensitive boundary areas.

The main value of the method is clarity. The map maker can see the membership surface, change the threshold, measure the producer/user tradeoff, and display the uncertainty zone. That makes the boundary decision easier to explain. With repeated testing on more reference maps, the same fuzzy process could help compress and streamline part of the intense workflow that goes into map making while keeping the logic understandable.

References

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